

Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling for 2030 Computation

ARDC COMMUNITY CONNECT PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	XN002A
PROJECT START AND END DATES	July 2023 - December 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	AuScope LTD
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	NCI
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Rebecca Farrington

1.1 Background

The Cross-NCRIS National Data Assets program co-funded the ‘Geophysics 2030: Building a National High-Resolution Geophysics Reference Collection for 2030 Computation’ (Geophysics2030) project. At completion, Geophysics2030 i) trialled publishing vertically integrated geophysical datasets, making both raw datasets and successive levels of derivative data products available online in a new international self-describing data standard (first published in 2022); ii) co-located these datasets/data products with HPC computing resources required to process datasets at scale; and iii) developed new community software and environments allowing researchers to exploit the new data sets at high-resolution on a continental-scale.

The ARDC, AuScope, NCI and TERN-funded project created a new high-performance dataset. It introduced a new, world-leading community platform that allows researchers to combine high-performance computing, high-resolution datasets, and flexible software workflows. World-leading innovation was evidenced by new projects in collaboration with leading international researchers, including Jared Peacock, the United States Geological Survey-based leader of the latest standards for Magnetotelluric (MT) data¹ and Karl Kappler, DIAS Geophysics, who leads the development of ‘Aurora’², a National Science Foundation (USA) funded open-source software package for processing MT data using the new MTH5 standards.

This Community Connect project, in partnership with NCI and AuScope, proposed to develop, deliver, and distribute a 2-day ‘Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling for 2030 Computation’ workshop in 2023. The training packages will consist of two parts, i) the utilisation of NCI for Geophysics processing and modelling, and ii) developing workflows for coupling Geophysical software, compute environments and datasets.

Through previous engagement with the Geophysics community, we knew users of the 2030 Geophysics Collection were experts in their fields of geophysics data acquisition, processing and modelling. The community had high levels of computer literacy and deep technical skills in geophysics and research expertise. The workshop was targeted to support this advanced community and facilitate the usage of large co-located datasets and high-performance computing at the NCI HPC/cloud platform.

¹ Peacock, J., Kappler, K., Heagy, L., Ronan, T., Kelbert, A., & Frassetto, A. (2022). MTH5: An archive and exchangeable data format for magnetotelluric time series data. *Computers & Geosciences*, 162, 105102. DOI: 10.1016/j.cageo.2022.105102

² Kappler, K., Egbert, G., Frassetto, A., Heagy, L., Kelbert, A., Keyson, L., Oldenburg, D., Peacock, J., & Ronan, T., 2022. Aurora: An open source magnetotelluric data processing package in Python linking MTH5 to EMTF XML. Abstract, 25th EM Induction Workshop, Çeşme, Turkey, September 11-17, 2022

1.2 Achievement of project aims

This project proposed to develop, deliver, and distribute a 2-day ‘Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling for 2030 Computation’ workshop in 2023.

Develop

The training workshop consisted of utilising NCI for Geophysics processing and modelling and developing workflows for coupling Geophysical software, compute environments, and datasets.

The workshop was attended by Australia’s leading geophysics data processing, modelling, and analysis researchers drawn from leading researchers in academia, government (state, territory, and national geological surveys), CSIRO, and industry; see Table 1 for details. While Australia has a relatively strong capability in Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling, the international community is small and fundamentally relies on global experts from international locations. As introduced above, Jared Peacock and Karl Kappler are international leaders within the Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling community. Their expertise is globally unique and critical for training the Australian community in next-generation data processing and modelling. Additionally, this international engagement and collaboration ensured that the training content produced by this project has a natural international footprint.

Delivery

The workshop was delivered face-to-face at the NCI’s ANU-based facility, allowing Australian Geophysics Research Data experts, listed in Table 1 below, to gather for an intensive 3-day workshop, along with USA-based Geophysics Research Data experts Jared Peacock and Karl Kappler. In addition to the named partners, expert Geophysicists from all state geological surveys, Geoscience Australia and the AuScope Geophysics community were invited and comprised expert researchers and educators, developers and users of key geophysical data and software processing and modelling packages. Locating the workshop at ANU ensured attendees had access to the expert data and computing specialists in Geophysical data curation and computing provided by NCI.

All expert researchers were required to contribute face-to-face throughout the workshop - either through collaborative development and delivery of training material or through the parallel user-acceptance testing that occurred in the delivery of the workshop. Additionally, it is impracticable for international researchers to participate remotely in a full 2-day technical workshop. A 2-day technical hands-on workshop for research experts spread between Perth and the USA is not practical unless it occurs face-to-face.

AuScope and NCI provided in-kind support for the workshop, including leveraging the same data, computing and geophysics experts as for the original 2030 Geophysics Collection project to provide both

communication, technical and leadership support. The preparation, delivery and distribution of the workshop and its products, was likewise resources from the current team. In-kind support was provided by universities, state geological surveys, Geoscience Australia and CSIRO for the development and delivery of the workshop content. The experts, each familiar with a specific software package already installed on the NCI geophysics environment, shared their experience on using it on the NCI platform. Other experts will introduce new software packages that are currently being tested on NCI.

Distribute

By working with this advanced community to test and develop training materials, these can be reused by a less experienced community. The workshop content will be captured, curated and distributed as training material for ongoing asynchronous use. At completion, the project delivered sustainable online user guides, support articles, FAQs and training modules including notebooks. These online resources have undergone user acceptance testing by our expert researcher community, with all material made sustainably accessible for reuse through the NCI Geophysics Specialised Environment, Opus NCI's Public Documentation Home and findable on DReSA.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1. Project outputs

The Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling for 2030 Computation workshop was held in at ANU's Marie Reay Teaching Centre on the 21st and 22nd of November, with community meetings held at NCI and Geoscience Australia on the 23rd of November. The participant list and agenda are detailed below in Tables 1 and 2. Figure X shows the results from our participant survey.

Participants were delivered tutorial-style presentations and examples throughout the workshop. Participants were provided access to NCI's GADI Australian Research Environment (ARE) via AuScope's partnership share. Each participant could view and execute a range of notebooks using multiple GADI processors, NCI Geophysics environment and datasets made accessible by Geophysics2030.

Workshop Attendees				Workshop Organisers			
1	Wenping Jiang	GA	Survey	1	Dr Lesley Wyborn	NCI	NCRIS
2	Babak Hejrani	GA	Survey	2	Dr Nigel Rees	NCI	NCRIS
3	Ravin Deo	GA	Survey	3	Dr Rui Yang	NCI	NCRIS
4	A.Yusen Ley	GA	Survey	4	Ms Jo Coucher	NCI	NCRIS
5	Roger Miller	GA	Survey	5	Dr Hannes Hollmann	NCI	NCRIS
6	Sasha Banaszczyk	GSWA	Survey	6	Dr Rebecca Farrington	AuScope	NCRIS
7	Reza Ebrahim	GSWA	Survey	7	Dr Ben Evans	NCI	NCRIS
8	Huaiyu Yuan	GSWA	Survey				
9	Tania Dhu	NTGS	Survey	Key Presenters			
10	Peter Eagleton	NTGS	Survey	1	Dr Jared Peacock	USGA	Survey
11	Mark Duffert	MRT	Survey	2	Dr Karl Kappler	Dias	Industry
12	Isaac Evinemi	MRT	Student	3	Dr Janelle Simpson	GSQ	Survey
13	Astrid Carlton	GSNSW	Survey	4	Dr Stephan Thiel	CSIRO	NGRO
14	Sam Matthews	GSNSW	Survey	5	Dr Hoël Seillé	CSIRO	NGRO
15	Dominic Brown	GSQ	Survey	6	Dr Anand Ray	GA	Survey
16	Sasha Aivazpourporgo	GSQ	Survey	7	Dr Sheng Wang	ANU	University
17	Ao Chang (Ollie)	QUT	University	8	Dr Voon Hui Lai	ANU	University
18	Ben Kay	UA	University	9	Dr Robert Pickle	ANU	University
19	Bruce Goleby	OPM Consulting	Consultant				
20	Sinan Ozaydin	University of Sydney	University				
21	Fatemeh Amirpoorsaeed	Monash (Student), Rio Tinto	University				
22	Jianwen He	ANU (Student)	University				

Table 1 Face-2-face participants of Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling for 2030 Computation workshop

Time	Presenter	Topic
DAY 1:- Geophysics Data in 2030 and NCI HPC Environments (Tuesday 21 November: ANU)		
09:00 - 09:05	Rebecca Farrington (AuScope)	Welcome, Introductions and Acknowledgement to Country
09:05 - 09:15	Janelle Simpson (GSQ)	Purpose of Workshop
09:15 - 09:35	Lesley Wyborn (NCI)	FAIR Geophysics Data For 2030 computation: what are the key considerations
09:35 - 09:50	Jo Croucher (NCI)	Vertical Integration of MT Data Assets at NCI and elsewhere
09:50 - 10:00	Hannes Hollmann (NCI)	What were the key gotchas and what do we have to improve.
10:00 - 10:15	Lesley, Jo, Hannes	General discussion and questions
10:15 - 11:00	Jared Peacock (USGS)	MTH5, MT Metadata
11:00 - 11:15	Morning Tea (provided)	
11:15 - 12: 30	Nigel Rees (NCI)	Introduction to NCI's Australian Research Environment (ARE) & Specialised Software Environments.
12:30 - 01:30	Lunch (not provided)	
DAY 1: - From Time Series to Transfer Functions (Tuesday: 21 November - ANU)		
01:30 - 03:00	Karl Kappler (Dias)	Aurora
03:00 - 03:15	Afternoon Tea (provided)	
03:15 - 04.45	Jared Peacock (USGS)	MTPy 2.0
03:15 - 04.45	Jared Peacock (USGS)	MTPy 2.0
04:45 - 05.30	Rui Yang (NCI)	Introduction to AI/ML Specialised Environments available at the NCI
06:00 - 09.00	Informal dinner Badger & Co – Uni Pub – ANU (attendees pay)	
DAY 2: MT and Generic Modelling Codes (Wednesday: 22 November - ANU)		
8:30 - 9:30	Janelle Simpson (GSQ) and Stephan Thiel (CSIRO): ModEM	
9:30 - 10:30	Jared Peacock (USGS)	SimPEG
10:30 - 10:45	Morning Tea (provided)	
10:45 - 11:45	Hoël Seillé, (CSIRO)	MT Probabilistic inversion
11:45 - 12:45	Anandaroop Ray (GA)	HiQGA: A fully featured inversion codebase focusing on AEM
12:45 - 1:30	Lunch (not provided)	
DAY 2: PS and DAS (Wednesday 22 November: ANU)		
1:30 - 2:15	Robert Pickle (RSES, ANU)	Overview of AusPass - the Australian Passive Seismic Server and its use on NCI
2:15 - 3:15	Sheng Wang (RSES, ANU)	Examples HPC processing of PS data
3:15 - 3:30	Afternoon Tea (provided)	
3:30 - 4:30	Voon Lai (RSES, ANU)	DAS
4:30 - 5:00	Rebecca Farrington (AuScope)	Accessing and Using the AuScope Share at NCI, key takeaways
DAY 3: AM - Geophysics Data in 2030 and NCI HPC Environments (Thursday 23 November)		
9:30 - 12:30	Jared Peacock (USGS), Karl Kapper (SSI), Surveys, AuScope, NCI, ASEG	Tour of the NCI facility and Brainstorming session: Where to Next? Can we build an Australian FAIR National Online Geophysics Data Platform integrating all data for all: Benefits and Challenges
DAY 3: PM - Field Data Acquisition and Data Delivery (Thursday 24 November)		
Location:	Geoscience Australia (101 Jerrabomberra Ave, Symonston) and online	
2:00 - 2.50	Penny Crook, Shawn Ross (Fieldmark):	Dirt to Desktop For Geophysics: an Introduction to Fieldmark.
3:00 - 3:50	All interested parties: Current methods of delivery of MT data, including demonstration by Jared Peacock of the USGS delivery system	
4:00 - 5:00	Jared Peacock, Karl Kapper:	SEG invited talk, "Potential global Interactive workflow for MT data using open-source packages and HPC"

Table 2 Agenda for Geophysical Research Data Processing and Modelling for 2030 Computation Workshop

Figure 1 Results for real-time participant survey

I learnt something that is directly applicable to my work.

A good range of subject domains were represented...

How much of the information presented at the workshop was of interest to you?

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

The content delivered within the workshop is openly available to the research community through DeRESA. The software and research data environments will be actively maintained by the NCI team and the ongoing AuScope-NCI partnership

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment.

Many of the current standards and processing methods were developed in the last century and do not allow for the utilisation of existing large scale and high-resolution datasets, nor do they enable innovative, transparent, replicable research. A long-term impact of this project, through engagement with influential academic, government and CSIRO researchers, was expected to be the increased uptake of new data standards and new high resolution, large scale geophysical data processing methods.

5.1 Research Outcomes Planning

As part of the Geophysics 2030 project, project representatives worked with Dr Laure Haak to generate an [impact reporting plan](#) for the Geophysics 2030 project. A plan is therefore in place for the completion of the Geophysics 2030 '[Project Impact Report](#)' template at 12 and 24 months after project conclusion. This includes systems and workflows to capture metrics and surveys related to the impact of project outputs.

Research outcomes associated with the Community Connect project will be incorporated into the Geophysics 2030 impact reports. For example, a Menti participant survey has already been completed by attendees of the Community Connect project (see Figure 1).